

NAGRIKAL

CITIZENS VOICES
FOR AND FROM
SMALL CITIES

**MAY
2024**

RISE IN TEMPERATURE & HEATWAVES IN SMALL AND MID-SIZED CITIES

Part of Nagrikal Series -

Frontlines of climate change: Small and mid-sized Cities

*A study on where small Indian cities stand in terms of climate
change impacts and data availability*

NAGRIKA

About Nagrika

Nagrika is a think-tank enabling citizens in small and mid-sized cities. We create knowledge that shapes unique, authentic and resilient cities. Through this knowledge, we mainstream the voice of citizens in decision making.

We co-create accessible and free knowledge resources for citizens and city governments. We have been creating knowledge about smaller cities from a small city. Much of this knowledge did not exist before and we strongly believe that what we are creating is needed by many but created by none. Our interventions have made it possible to understand these cities better. Slowly and steadily, our work has ensured that smaller cities become part of policy agendas of urban policy making.

We build a sense of ownership and community in small towns while strengthening city - policy - citizen relationship by demystifying public policy. Our activities include creating and amplifying voices from smaller cities, putting spotlight on developments in smaller cities, analyzing larger trends for their impact on smaller cities and various other initiatives that push the boundaries of thought and action in our small towns.

Nagrika Team

Tarun Sharma | Co Founder

Yutika Vora | Co Founder

Nimisha Samadhiya | Senior Research Associate

Arundhati Chowdhury | Research Associate

Our Partners

This report has partly been supported by a grant from Rohini Nilekani Philanthropies Foundation.

This report is a living document and will be regularly updated. It is being informed by our ongoing research and co-created knowledge from various actors and institutions across multiple smaller cities.

About the Series

This Nagrikal Series examines the relationship between climate change and cities, especially small and mid-sized cities*. The series attempts to explore the dual roles of such cities- cities as contributors to and sufferers of climate change.

This Nagrikal series discusses some of the important impacts of climate change, like poor air quality, rising sea levels, rising temperatures, and increasing heatwaves. It serves as an explainer of how climate change induces these impacts in our cities. Highlighting the limited share of knowledge about small cities, climate data availability, and monitoring, this series urges us to rethink the future of small cities in the face of climate change. By bringing forth the facts and figures that are less talked about, we hope to shift the discourse from our current understanding in an effort to build resilient small cities.

From defining the role of cities, especially the smaller cities, in climate change to exploring the share of such cities in research studies, climate data availability, and monitoring, the series aligns with our objective of creating knowledge for smaller cities to drive meaningful action. The series is divided into four parts. Part one explains the relationship between cities and climate change; Part two talks about the declining air quality in small cities; Part three focuses on the rise in temperatures and heatwaves; and Part four highlights the cities that are at risk of sea level rise. Parts two, three, and four use small cities as case studies to explain the consequences of the respective impacts. Some of the key insights and findings from each of the parts are shared in the next section.

We invite readers to engage with the findings of this report and join us in the collective effort to reimagine the future of small cities in the face of climate change. We believe that stakeholders at every level can make a significant change by utilising the insights provided in this publication. By understanding the city specific challenges, let us co-create innovative solutions to combat climate change impacts for a sustainable and resilient future.

We hope that this report will not just inform but also initiate a conversation about the challenges faced by small cities with regards to climate change in the policy discourse and climate action strategies, which is currently missing.

**Small and Mid-sized in this report refer to cities that have a population of up to 2.5 million.*

Table of contents

List of Abbreviations	1
Glossary	2
Summary and Key Insights	3
Climate Change and Temperature Rise	4
Record-breaking High Temperatures	5
Rise in Annual Average Temperatures of small and mid-sized cities	5
Extreme Heat in India: Increase in number of Heatwave days	6
Exposure to extreme heat in India	8

Small and mid-sized cities under Heat stress	10
Associated extreme weather events	11
Share of small and mid-sized cities in Weather monitoring	11
Share of small and mid-sized cities in Continuous Data Availability	13
Share of small and mid-sized cities in 2022 Research studies	14
Share of small and mid-sized cities in Heat Action Plans	14
City level Actions to fight Heat stress	15
Conclusion	16
Case Study: Chandigarh	20
Repository	22

List of Abbreviations

°C	Degree Celsius
IMD	India Meteorological Department
MoSPI	Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation
NDMA	National Disaster Management Authority
DEWS	Drought Early Warning System
IIT	Indian Institute of Technology
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature
UHI	Urban Heat Island
HAP	Heat Action Plan
MET	Meteorological
GHAR	Green Houses at Affordable Rates
PMAY	Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana
BEE	Bureau of Energy Efficiency
ECBC	Energy Conservation Building Code

Glossary

Heatwave	A period of extremely hot weather conditions, causing adverse effects on the environment.
Drought	A prolonged dry period, caused as a result of the depletion of soil moisture, that can last for days, months, or years.
Extreme Heat	Temperatures of a particular location during summer that are much hotter and/or humid than its normal average temperature.
Normal Temperature	Also known as the baseline temperatures, normal temperature is derived from the Climatological Normals of 1981-2020. The climatological data based on the period 1981-2020 are used to calculate the normal temperature.
Climatological Normal	Climatological normal is the average of climatological data which serves as a benchmark to compare current observations and is used to predict climate conditions for a location. Climatological normals are updated every decade. The recent publication includes climatological normals for the period 1981-2020 for 405 meteorological observatories.
Annual Average Temperature	The temperature derived by calculating the mean average of the coldest and the hottest month of the year.
Flash droughts	Flash droughts are fast compared to conventional drought events and can impact a larger region within a period of 2 to 3 weeks.
Weather Station	A facility with a set of instruments or equipment that are used to monitor atmospheric conditions, along with providing regular weather forecasts and data regarding the climate.

Summary and Key Insights

Rising Temperatures and Heatwaves:

- a. The report highlights a significant global and national increase in temperatures, with the average rate of temperature rise doubling since 1981. Cities worldwide, including India, have experienced extreme temperatures, with some reaching as high as 53.6°C.
- b. In India, small and mid-sized cities have recorded unprecedented high temperatures, with 2023 being the second hottest year in 122 years. The report also discusses the increase in the frequency and intensity of heat waves, highlighting the fact that the duration of heat waves has extended significantly over the years.

Impact on Small and Mid-Sized Cities:

- a. Small and mid-sized cities in India are particularly vulnerable to the adverse effects of rising temperatures due to their inadequate infrastructure and resources to effectively mitigate and manage extreme heat.
- b. These cities have seen a significant rise in their annual average maximum temperatures, with an observed increase of over 9°C in the past decade compared to their normal baseline temperatures.
- c. The report also highlights the fact that these cities are experiencing higher temperatures for longer durations and are approaching dangerous levels of heat and humidity.

Socio-Economic Impacts and Policy Responses:

- a. The socio-economic impacts of rising temperatures and heatwaves are profound, including increased mortality rates, especially among vulnerable populations like the elderly, and significant economic losses due to reduced labour hours and income.
- b. The report also discusses further aggravation of drought conditions and water stress due to rising temperatures and inadequate rainfall.
- c. It also highlights some of the policy responses that some cities have developed. For example, some cities have devised Heat Action Plans to mitigate the effects of heatwaves, although the effectiveness and implementation of these plans vary.
- d. The report also highlights significant gaps in weather monitoring and data availability, particularly in small and mid-sized cities, which hamper effective local planning and response to heatwaves.

Rise in temperature & Heatwaves in small and mid-sized cities

Climate Change and Temperature Rise

The rise in temperature is regarded as one of the primary impacts of climate change; however, climate change itself is often specifically referred to as rising global temperatures. As per recent numbers, the average rate of temperature increase per decade (both land and ocean) is over three times the rate since 1982- from 0.06°C to 0.20°C. In recent years, cities worldwide have been facing extreme temperatures as high as 53.6°C. With an average temperature increase of 1.45°C from the pre-industrial period, 2023 was recorded as the hottest year.

In India, many small and mid-sized cities saw record-breaking summer temperatures in 2023 as well as 2022 and are witnessing a gradual increase in their average temperatures over the years. This report, as part of the Climate Change in Small Cities series, delves deeply into this topic, providing further exploration and analysis that highlights the disproportionate impact of heatwaves on these smaller urban areas compared to larger cities. The analysis reveals that these cities are often less equipped with the infrastructure and resources necessary to mitigate and manage extreme heat, making them more vulnerable to the adverse effects of rising temperatures.

The maximum temperature in India is increasing by 0.1 Degrees Celsius per decade.

Figure 1: Share of Small cities that observed record breaking temperatures during May 2022
Source: News Reports

Record-breaking High Temperatures

According to the India Meteorological Department (IMD), the maximum temperature in the country has increased by 1°C, while the minimum temperature has risen by 0.36°C on average over the last 10 decades. This rapid increase in the maximum temperature has led to an increase in the frequency of heatwaves, and cities are now witnessing record-breaking high temperatures. It is observed that most of these cities are located in the northern part of the country.

As per IMD, 2023 was India's second hottest year since 1901, that is second in 122 years. According to the annual summary released by IMD for the year 2023, 96 cities recorded the highest maximum temperatures, ranging from 23°C to as high as 43.9°C. Out of these 96 cities, only one is a big city. It is also observed that 13 cities recorded temperatures above 40°C. Lumding, a town located in Assam recorded 40°C twice in the year, while Madurai, located in Tamil Nadu, crossed 40°C twice in the month of August.

In 2022, around 35 cities witnessed temperatures of 45°C and above in the month of May, out of which 34 were small and mid-sized. The highest temperature, 49°C, was recorded in Banda, a small city in Uttar Pradesh. The city previously recorded similar high temperatures in 1994. Cities that recorded temperatures above 47°C included Churu, Hissar, Nowgong, Jhansi, and Pilani.

Rise in Annual Average Temperatures of small and mid-sized cities

To analyse the rise in the annual average

Figure 2: Rise in average Maximum Temperature in: a) Srinagar and b) Patiala from 2014 to 2023

Source: IMD Annual Summary

maximum temperatures of small and mid-sized cities, we have used the data released by IMD in the annual summary reports from 2014 to 2023. The annual report covers 152 cities across the country; however, 7 did not have continuous data available for the selected time period, so the number of cities considered in this analysis is 145. Out of these 145 cities, only 11 are big cities. Over the course of these ten years, we observed an average temperature rise of over 9°C in the 134 small and mid-sized cities compared to

their normal baseline temperature. For cities like Srinagar and Patiala, this increase is over 14°C and 15°C, respectively.

About 137 cities have witnessed an increase of over 5°C in the annual average temperature in the past ten years, of which 126 are small and mid-sized. Similarly, out of the 72 cities that recorded an increase of over 10°C, 70 are small and mid-sized. This indicates that a larger share of small and mid-sized cities are more vulnerable to higher temperatures and heat stress in India.

Smaller cities are more vulnerable to higher temperatures & heat stress compared to bigger cities!

Figure 3: Share of Small cities in rise in annual average maximum temperatures
 Source: IMD Annual Summary

The baseline temperatures, also known as normal temperatures, were derived from the Climatological Normals of 1981–2020. The climatological data based on the period 1981–2020 are used to calculate the normal and hence the anomaly, {that is, the difference (rise or decline): actual average temperature in 20XX minus normal temperature based on data from 1981–2020}.

The average minimum temperature in the month of December 2023 was the highest since 1901, with an anomaly of +1.72°C. The observed average maximum, average minimum, and mean temperatures for the month were 27.04°C, 16.16°C, and 21.60°C, respectively, against the normal of 26.53°C, 14.44°C, and 20.49°C.

Extreme Heat in India: Increase in number of Heatwave days

According to a World Bank report published in 2022, India is experiencing higher temperatures for longer durations, and in the coming ten years, the country may face heatwaves beyond human survivability limits. The IPCC’s sixth assessment report has already warned India about the likelihood of frequent and intense heatwaves in the next decade if carbon emissions remain high. Additionally, the report finds that small and mid-sized cities like Bhubaneswar and Patna are “approaching dangerous levels of heat and humidity”.

Figure 4: Average number of Heat Wave days reported in India from 2010 to 2022
 Source: EnviStats 2023 | Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation

India experiences heatwaves most often from March to June, with May usually marking their peak. 2023 saw heatwaves arriving by March 03, which continued until May third week. Over 60% of the country witnessed temperatures higher than normal on April 18. As per IMD's annual summary reports, about 14 cities experienced a maximum temperature above normal by 4.4°C for 6-10 days in April. This figure rose to 29 cities in June. For 11 cities, the number of days with a maximum temperature above normal increased to 11-15 days in June. As per the assessment of extreme weather events by the Centre for Science and Environment, India experienced heatwaves for 49 days from March to June.

third-highest number since 2010 and over six times higher than in 2021. The highest number of heatwave days were reported in Rajasthan, Punjab, Haryana, and Jharkhand. These states accounted for 48% of the country's total number of heatwave days in 2022, while in 2021, their share was only 22%.

Highest number of heatwave days were reported in Rajasthan, Punjab, Haryana in 2022!

Figure 6: Top States with highest average number of Heatwave days reported in 2022

Source: EnviStats 2023 | Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation

Since 1992, over 24,000 people have died because of heat waves in India.

Figure 5: Deaths caused by extreme heat in India from 2012 to 2021

Source: National Crime Records Bureau data

Meanwhile, 2022 experienced heatwaves from March 11, which continued until the last week of May. The Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MoSPI) released data indicating that 2022 recorded 190 heatwave days. This was the

For 2023, February and August were the warmest in 123 years. Many cities witnessed record breaking temperatures during these months. For example, Bhuj recorded above 40°C temperature in February, while 7 cities (all small) crossed above 40°C temperature in August. Similarly, for the year 2022, March and April

turned out to be the hottest months in India since 1901. By April 29, 2022, 70% of the country had been affected by the heatwave. Notably, the IMD dashboard in the hazard atlas provides heatwave data only for four months- April to July- indicating that heatwaves in the month of March are 'abnormal'.

A study by IMD revealed that India saw a 45% increase in the number of heatwave days from 1981-90 to 2011-20, rising from 413 to 600 days. At present, the duration of heatwaves in the country is 2 to 4 days on average. However, the latest findings by IMD indicate that the duration has increased by 2.5 days from 1961 to 2021 due to global warming. Furthermore, the study projects an anticipated increase in heatwave duration of 12 to 18 days by 2060.

India saw a 45% increase in the number of heatwave days from 1981-90 to 2011-20!

Figure 7: Increase in the number of heatwave days from 1981-90 to 2011-20
 Source: IMD

Heatwaves are defined based on either the actual temperature or the deviation from normal temperature. In India, a heatwave is considered when the maximum temperature of a station reaches at least 40°C or more for the plains, 37°C for coastal areas, and 30°C for hilly regions.

IMD declares a heatwave or a severe heatwave based on the following two criteria:

1. Based on Departure from Normal

- Heat Wave: Departure from normal is 4.5°C to 6.4°C
- Severe Heat Wave: Departure from normal is above 6.4°C

2. Based on Actual Maximum Temperature

- Heat Wave: Actual maximum temperature is 45°C and above
- Severe Heat Wave: Actual maximum temperature is 47°C and above

IMD issues colour coded warnings based on the impacts of the heatwave in collaboration with the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA). For example, green is used for 'no action needed' when the maximum temperature is near normal, while orange is used for 'be prepared' when temperatures are high and severe heatwave conditions persist for 2 days.

	No Action: Max. temperatures are near normal
	Be Updated: Heatwave at isolated pockets persists on 2 days
	Be Prepared: Severe Heatwaves likely to persist for 2 or more days
	Take Action: Total number of Heatwaves days likely to exceed 6 days

Figure 8: Colour coded Heatwave warnings by IMD
 Source: IMD

Exposure to extreme heat in India

As per the 2021 Lancet report, India experienced 15% more extreme heat in 2019 compared to 1990. It further finds that

globally, senior citizens (aged 65 and above) were exposed to heatwaves for an additional 3.1 billion days compared to the 1986–2005 baseline average. India was among the top 5 countries where senior citizens, or the vulnerable population, were most affected. A 2022 study published in the Lancet revealed that the country has seen a 55% increase in deaths due to extreme heat from 2000–2004 to 2017–2021. It also reveals that India lost 167.2 billion potential labour hours in 2021 and, as a result, suffered an income loss equivalent to 5.4% of the GDP. As per a report, heatwaves claimed the lives of two people on average every day in India during the summer months of April, May, and June in the year 2023.

received about 36% less rainfall than normal. An analysis by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration further shows that more than 25% of the country continued to face drought conditions throughout December 2023.

Furthermore, a 2021 study finds that 17 Indian cities are among the top 50 places globally with the highest rise in exposure to extreme heat and humidity from 1983 to 2016. Delhi and Kolkata, two major cities, are among the top four cities, with an increase of 553 million and 522 million person-days of extreme heat during the period. The study defines person-days as the annual increase in the urban population exposed to extreme heat. Apart from the bigger cities, small and mid-sized cities have also shown significant increases. Agra has experienced an increase of 60 million person-days, whereas Gorakhpur has experienced an increase of 48 million person-days.

India has **seen a 55% increase in deaths due to extreme heat** from 2000–2004 to 2017–2021.

Source : The Third Pole

Apart from socio-economic losses, India is also suffering from drought-like conditions that threaten food productivity and water security. Data from the Drought Early Warning System (DEWS) shows that over 21% of the country's land area suffered from drought-like conditions in 2021. While it was only 7.6% in 2020. DEWS is a real-time drought monitoring platform managed by the Indian Institute of Technology, Gandhinagar. India faced the driest August in 2023 in the past 123 years, as the country

Figure 9: India in Global Trends for extreme heat
 Source: Research studies

Small and Mid-sized cities under Heat stress

With a significant increase in the duration of abnormal temperatures and heatwaves, several cities, particularly small and mid-sized ones, are facing extreme heat stress. As per a 2022 study that analysed the temperature variations from April 2021 to 2022 in ten Indian cities, it was observed that small and mid-sized cities like Shimla and Bhopal have experienced a higher increase in the duration of extreme

temperature conditions compared to larger cities like Delhi, Mumbai, and Kolkata.

Popularly known as the Queen of Hills, Shimla in Himachal Pradesh recorded the highest maximum temperatures of 42°C and 44°C during the month of April in 2021 and 2022, respectively. These temperatures are more than twice the normal temperature for the month of April, as per the climatological normals. The study highlights that the city experienced temperatures above 40°C for 17 days in

The hill city has been **facing severe heatwaves** as the **temperature is continuously rising above 40°C** during summers.

Highest max. temp. during April 2021: **40-42°C**

Highest max. temp. during April 2022: **40-44°C**

Rise in number of days with extreme temp. conditions: **183.33%**

The city **experienced extreme temperatures for 28 days** in April 2022. **At 43.3°C, Bhopal recorded 2nd highest day** in April in the decade.

Highest max. temp. during April 2021: **40-43°C**

Highest max. temp. during April 2022: **40-43°C**

Rise in number of days with extreme temp. conditions: **180%**

The city was **among the five hottest cities** in Uttar Pradesh in April 2022. **At 45°C, the city recorded its hottest April day** ever in 100 years.

Highest max. temp. during April 2021: **40-42°C**

Highest max. temp. during April 2022: **40-45°C**

Rise in number of days with extreme temp. conditions: **145.45%**

Figure 10: Rise in number of days with extreme temperature conditions in two small cities, Shimla & Bhopal, and one big city, Lucknow

Source: Summers like no other | Greenpeace 2022

2022, compared to only 6 days in 2021.

Similarly, Bhopal, the capital city of Madhya Pradesh, experienced high temperatures between 40–43°C for 28 days in April 2022, compared to only 10 days in April 2021. Both Shimla and Bhopal have shown an increase of around 180% in the number of days with extreme temperature conditions. On the other hand, bigger cities like Lucknow and Delhi have shown increases of 145% and 122%, respectively.

Associated extreme weather events

Extreme heat conditions coupled with a lack of rainfall increase the frequency of droughts- a prolonged dry period (caused as a result of the depletion of soil moisture) that can last for days, months, or years. Even though drought is a natural phenomenon that occurs due to natural changes in our climate, human induced climate change has made urban areas more susceptible to droughts.

As per reports, India's drought prone area has expanded by 57% since 1977, affecting 50 million people each year. About one-third of India's districts have endured more than four droughts in the past ten years. Recently, between 2020 and 2022, approximately two-thirds of the nation experienced drought. A 2021 study by IIT Gandhinagar predicts that a warming climate will increase the frequency of flash droughts by up to 7 to 8 folds in the country, which will have a negative impact on groundwater availability and crop production. In contrast to conventional drought events, flash droughts are fast and can impact a larger region within a period of 2 to 3 weeks. As a result, many of the cities are at risk of facing severe water stress.

According to the WWF Water Risk Filter, about one third of the 100 cities in the world that will face a 'grave water risk' by 2050 are in India. Jaipur tops the Indian list, followed by Indore and Thane. Out of the 30 Indian cities on the list, 21 are small and mid-sized cities.

India's **drought prone area has expanded by 57%** since 1977, **affecting 50 million people** each year.

Source : Scroll.in

Share of Small and mid sized cities in Weather monitoring

The India Meteorological Department, or IMD, is the principal agency in India responsible for monitoring and forecasting weather. Established in 1875, IMD is also one of the six Regional Specialized Meteorological Centres of the World Meteorological Organization and is responsible for naming, forecasting, and issuing warnings for tropical cyclones in the Northern Indian Ocean. IMD observes and analyses six weather parameters- temperature, cloudiness, atmospheric pressure, precipitation, wind, and humidity- and issues a daily weather bulletin that provides an overview of the weather conditions observed across the country. It also issues a weather forecast for the next five days and special warnings

for citizens for heat waves, cold waves, cyclones, etc.

- | | |
|-------------------------|------------------|
| 1- Temperature | 4- Precipitation |
| 2- Cloudiness | 5- Wind |
| 3- Atmospheric Pressure | 6- Humidity |

Figure 11: Six weather parameters to observe daily weather conditions & Contents of daily bulletin by IMD

Source: IMD

IMD monitors the weather through weather stations. Although the latest number of weather stations in the country is unclear, we have analysed the concentration of 405 weather stations based on the numbers given in the climatological normals of 1981-2020. Out of these 405 stations, 368 are located in urban centers across the country. It has been observed that about 95% of these weather stations are spread across 336 small and mid-sized cities, while the remaining 5% are located in the 12 big cities. Among the bigger cities, Delhi

has the highest number of weather stations (3), followed by Mumbai, Bangalore, and Kolkata (2 each). The highest number of stations located in a small city is two; these cities include Visakhapatnam, Jamshedpur, Vadodara, Belagavi, and Mangaluru.

Unlike the air quality monitoring stations, there are no prescribed population criteria that govern the number of weather stations to be installed in a city. The current network of weather stations covers only 348 urban centres, which is only 4% of the total urban centers in the country. This not only indicates the inadequacy of data monitoring and collection for a large share of urban centers in India but also highlights the risks people can face due to the unavailability of localised predictions. For example, the absence of a weather station in Panvel led to the deaths of 13 people, as IMD could not issue any heatwave warnings for the city in April 2023. The localised climatic conditions, also referred to as the micro-climate, depend on various local factors like topography, vegetation, and environmental variables such as temperature, moisture, and wind near the surface. Since land cover affects the micro-climate, changes in land use patterns due to human activities also have an impact on it. Since micro-climate is different from the climate of the overall region, the presence of weather monitoring stations at the local level is crucial to capturing the changes in the micro-climate and taking necessary local actions.

In addition to the daily bulletin for disseminating weather related information, IMD has established an integrated platform called The Climate Data Service Portal, which functions as a repository to acquire and disseminate climate data for the country.

Share of Small and mid sized cities in Continuous Data Availability

To analyse the continuity in data availability for small and mid-sized cities, we have considered the station wise annual temperature data released in the Annual Climate Summary report by IMD. The report not only records the annual average temperatures but also records the number of days or dates on which the city observed the highest temperature throughout the year based on real-time data. The report covers 152 cities in total, of which 141 are small and mid-sized cities. It is observed that the continuous annual temperature data for the last ten years (2014-2023) is available for 90% of the 141 small and mid-sized cities covered in the report. Whereas for 11 big cities, continuous data availability is 100%. For example, Madikeri, a small town in Karnataka, does not have annual temperature data for 2022 and 2023. Similar is the case with Malegaon, a small city in Maharashtra.

Continuous weather related data is crucial to understanding the changes in the local climate that occur over time. Even though there are 336 small and mid-sized cities that have been covered in the weather monitoring network, continuous data is available for only 141 of them. Though the reason behind the unavailability is unclear, in the past few years, there have been reports of poor maintenance and weather stations remaining defunct. For example, weather stations in several cities in Haryana remained nonfunctional for months, as per a 2019 report. The lack of operational weather stations not only hinders data availability but also affects predictions related to weather, which in turn impacts the lives of the residents. For example, the automatic weather stations

Figure 12: Share of Small cities as compared to Big cities

Source : IMD & Research studies

installed in Thiruvananthapuram failed to provide essential data and warnings related to heavy rainfall as they were lying defunct due to a lack of maintenance. As a result, the city experienced one of the worst floods, leaving the residents stranded.

Share of Small cities in 2022 Research studies

We have reviewed 50 journal articles (both national and international) published in 2022 with reference to the rise in temperature, heat waves, heat stress, and the urban heat island effect in an Indian city to analyze the availability of knowledge on small and mid-sized cities. It is observed that over 50% of these studies focus on the bigger cities like Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata, Chennai, and Hyderabad. While only 30% focus exclusively on small and mid-sized cities like Chandigarh, Rajkot, and Sonipat. Around 16% of the studies focused on both small and big cities. It is interesting to note that 30% of the studies mentioned the heat stress in Delhi, indicating the prime focus on the city in the research landscape.

Of the 50 studies reviewed, 38% are focused on urban heat island (UHI) investigation and assessment. About 16% study the relationship of land use and UHI phenomenon, 12% focus on rise in surface temperatures, while 10% focus on heatwave assessment. Of 50 studies, 2 focus on heatwave prediction, 2 on Heat Vulnerability Index, while heat-related health risk of heatwaves, awareness towards heatwaves and thermal comfort in urban spaces have one study each. We are currently updating this research gap for the recent years.

Share of Small cities in Heat Action Plans

The Heat Action Plans (HAPs) serve as an

important tool for the government to manage and reduce the impact of heatwaves on human life. The plans prescribe short term and long term response strategies, as well as the setting up of early warning systems and heat adaptation measures. According to the NCRB records, India recorded over 24,200 deaths between 1992 and 2015 due to heatwaves. The deadly 2010 heatwave, which led to over 1,300 deaths in Ahmedabad city, resulted in the preparation of the country's first HAP. Ahmedabad Municipal Corporation prepared the HAP in 2013 with the help of academic experts (both national and international) and insights learned from global practices on early warning systems. The plan was later updated in 2016. Since then, several cities across the country have taken up the initiative to prepare HAPs, taking Ahmedabad's HAP as a reference. In 2016, the NDMA prepared the national guidelines to help the cities prepare the HAPS. These guidelines were revised twice, first in 2017 and then in 2019.

The exact number of HAPs prepared in the country is still unclear. The number of cities preparing or those who have prepared HAPs has not been listed clearly on any platform, but as per a recent report, the central government is working with 23 states to develop and implement HAPs in around 130 cities. However, the names of these 130 cities have not yet been revealed. The Centre for Policy Research in its recent report titled *How Is India Adapting to Heatwaves?*, analysed 37 HAPs, of which 9 are at the city level, 13 at the district level, and 15 at the state level. For our analysis, we have considered 27 HAPs that were listed in different sources, including the above mentioned study and some of the news reports or on the NDMA website. Of these 27 HAPs, 23 are for small and mid-sized cities like Rewari, Rajkot, Vijayawada, and Bhubaneswar, while the

remaining three are for bigger cities, namely Ahmedabad, Surat, and Hyderabad.

City level Actions to fight Heat stress

After facing deadly heatwaves in 2010, with temperatures reaching a record breaking high of 46°C, Ahmedabad became the first city in India, as well as South Asia, to develop a Heat Action Plan. An analysis reveals that the city has successfully avoided 1,190 deaths per year due to the implementation of the plan. This success is not just attributed to the implementation of mitigating measures like cool roofs, early warnings, and community outreach but also to effective inter-agency coordination at the municipal level.

The Heat Action Plans are built upon four key pillars at the local level: building public awareness, establishing an early warning system and inter-agency coordination, capacity building of healthcare professionals, and reducing heat exposure through adaptive measures like the Cool Roofs program. The HAP emphasizes the importance of identifying the local causes of the temperature rise and the vulnerable groups within the city to tailor focused local actions.

Responsibilities and activities are distributed among various agencies based on different heat alert levels. More than 40% of the responsibility for managing heatwaves under HAPs is allocated to urban local bodies.

Figure 13: City level Actions to fight Heat stress under Heat Action Plans

Source: Heat Action Plan

In April 2023, Telangana launched Cool Roof Policy with an aim to drive state-wide adoption of cool roofs to make the state heat resilient. First of its kind in the country, the five-year policy includes mandatory installation of cool roofing materials as well as incorporating cooling materials in laying roads, footpaths, and cycle tracks. The policy is launched as a joint intervention of the municipal administration and urban development department.

Rajkot's Smart GHAR III (Green Housing at Affordable Rate) was launched in 2015 under Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY), for sustainable housing solutions as the city falls within the semi-arid region and undergoes scorching summers. Innovative measures like energy-efficient casement windows, enhanced ventilation, and reflective roofs, had been utilised to construct these homes. Final testing of these homes reported a 6°C decrease in the peak indoor temperature and an increase in the number of hours the room temperature remained below 30°C. The project has also deployed rooftop solar to operate elevators, street lights, and overhead tanks connected to municipal supply lines.

Under the Bureau of Energy Efficiency (BEE), the 2017 Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC) sets minimum energy standards for new commercial buildings having a connected load of 100 kW or contract demand of 120 Kilo volt-amperes or more. Such energy performance standards have been designed to address the unique challenges of India's growing commercial building sector. ECBC emphasises collaborative efforts among stakeholders for its successful adoption and implementation. With its technologically neutral approach, focus on renewable energy integration, and inclusion of passive design strategies, ECBC aims to promote sustainable development while ensuring occupant

comfort and environmental responsibility.

Rajkot became the **first city in the country** in 2020 to obtain the '**Green Building Certificate**' for its affordable housing scheme.

Source : Twitter

Conclusion

The rise in temperature is the most visible impact of climate change, so much so that climate change is often associated with only rising temperatures and extreme heat. Just like poor air quality, rise in temperature and change in climate are interdependent. Rising temperatures fuel climate change, while climate change induces frequent, intense heatwaves and abnormally high temperatures.

Abnormally high temperatures are becoming increasingly prevalent in small and mid-sized cities, affecting not only daytime temperatures but night time temperatures as well. These cities are witnessing record-breaking maximum temperatures, reaching as high as 49°C in Banda, and unusually high minimum temperatures, reaching as high as 18°C in Shimla. Shimla is also one of the small and mid-sized cities that has seen the highest percentage increase in the number of days with extremely high temperatures.

There are 7,935 towns and cities in India as per the 2011 census; however, the current

weather monitoring network covers only 363 of these. This indicates that about 95% of urban areas lack adequate weather-related data, which is important for localised predictions. In addition to this, for the small and mid-sized cities that have been covered in the weather monitoring network, the share of continuous data availability is still low compared to the bigger cities. Continuous data availability is necessary to determine the actual increase in the normal temperature of the cities to make them heat resilient.

References

- Climate.gov. 2023. "Climate Change: Global Temperature." Retrieved August 28, 2023.
- Yale Climate Connections. 2023. "Earth's 5th- or 6th-warmest year on record." Retrieved August 28, 2023.
- WMO. (2024, January 12). WMO confirms that 2023 smashes global temperature record. World Meteorological Organization WMO. Retrieved April 17, 2024.
- Times of India. 2022. "climate Change Led To Surge In Temperature In India."
- ENS. (2024, January 2). 2023 was India's second hottest since 1901: IMD | Bangalore News. The Indian Express. Retrieved April 17, 2024.
- Hindustan Times. 2022. "Delhi sees new record at 49°C, heatwave soars in many parts of India: 10 points."
- Outlook India. 2022. "UP's Banda Breaks 28-Yr-Old Temperature Record; Reels Under 49 Degree Celsius."
- IMD Pune. "Climate Research & Services, Pune." Retrieved August 28, 2023.
- IMD Pune. 2015. "CLIMATOLOGICAL NORMALS 1981 - 2010." Retrieved August 28, 2023.
- IMD. (2023, December 1). Climate Summary for the month of December 2023. IMD Pune. Retrieved April 17, 2024.
- World Bank. 2022. "Climate Investment Opportunities in India's Cooling Sector." Retrieved August 28, 2023
- ThePrint. 2021. "India to suffer more intense heat waves, heavier rainfall in future decades, IPCC report says."
- The Financial Express. 2022. "Climate change: Mumbai at high flood risk; Heat, humidity to make India uninhabitable if emissions not cut."
- Sangomla, A. (2024, February 13). South India may see early, intense heatwaves thanks to El Nino and global warming. Down To Earth. Retrieved April 17, 2024.
- Pandey, K. (2023, April 20). Heatwaves arrive early in 2023; hit 11 states from March 3 to April 18. Down To Earth. Retrieved April 17, 2024.
- Frontline. (2023, December 1). India saw extreme weather events almost every day from Jan to Sep 2023: report. Frontline. Retrieved April 17, 2024.
- CSE. (2023, September 30). CLIMATE. Centre for Science and Environment. Retrieved April 17, 2024.
- IMD. (2023, March 15). IMD Annual Report 2022. IMD. Retrieved August 28, 2023.
- MoSPI. 2023. "Heatwave days in 2022." Retrieved August 28, 2023.
- India Today. 2022. "March 2022 was India's hottest in 122 years, says weather department."
- India Today. 2022. "Hottest April in 122 years in northwest, central India, says weather office."
- IMD. "HAZARD ATLAS OF INDIA." Retrieved August 28, 2023.
- Scroll.in. 2022. "Why is the number of heatwave days rising in India? Scientists blame climate change."

The Wire. 2023. "Duration of Heatwaves in India Has Increased Over Last 30 years, Set to Rise Further. IMD."

IMD. "What is heat wave? Qualitatively, heat wave is a condition of air temperature which becomes fatal to human body when exposed." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

Gaon Connection. 2021. "India among the top 5 countries with highest exposure of vulnerable population to extreme heat : Lancet Report."

BBC. 2022. "India heatwave: High temperatures killing more Indians now, Lancet study finds."

Lavania, D. (2023, July 29). 250 died this summer due to heat wave | Agra News. *Times of India*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Down To Earth. 2021. "Drought scare looms large over a fifth of India."

IMD. (2023, September 2). Sub: Climate Summary for the month of August 2023 - 1. Monthly Rainfall Scenario (01 to 31 Aug, 2023). IMD. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Ra, S. (2024, January 23). A fourth of India faced drought conditions in December. *The Hindu BusinessLine*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Tuholske, C. et al. 2020. "Global urban population exposure to extreme heat." *PNAS*. Retrieved August 28, 2023.

Down To Earth. 2021. "Indian cities among places with highest rise in exposure to extreme heat. Study."

Greenpeace. (2022). "SUMMERS LIKE NONE OTHER." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

World Meteorological Organization. "Drought." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

India Today. 2022. "More and more droughts: How both India and the world is getting affected and what it will lead to."

Economic Times. 2021. "Warming will increase frequency of flash droughts in India: IIT Gandhinagar study."

Mongabay-India. 2021. "Flash droughts set to increase in India, finds study."

The Hindu. 2020. "30 Indian cities will face 'water risk' by 2050: report."

Ground Report. 2023. "10 Indian cities facing water scarcity in 2023 ."

IMD. "India Meteorological Department." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

RSMC. "Regional Specialized Meteorological Centres" Retrieved August 28, 2023.

IMD. "All India Weather Forecast Bulletin." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

IMD. "The Climate Data Service Portal." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

Acharya, P. (2023, April 18). Why IMD couldn't issue heatwave warning: No weather station in Panvel or Kharghar. *The Indian Express*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Pielke, R. A. (2024, February 20). Microclimate | Factors, Types, & Facts. *Britannica*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Wimberly, M. C. et.al. (2020, September 21). Land cover affects microclimate and temperature suitability for arbovirus transmission in an urban landscape. *NCBI*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

IMD. "Annual Climate Summary." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

Verma, S. (2019). IMD's automatic weather stations in Haryana not relaying weather data as batteries, sensors not replaced. *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Mohan, S. (2023). *Defunct Met stations leave Kerala at weather's mercy*. *New Indian Express*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

NDMA. 2020. "Beating the Heat." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

NRDC. 2016. "Ahmedabad Heat Action Plan." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

NIDM. 2019. "National Guidelines for Preparation of Action Plan." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

Rele, M., & Dhagey, J. (2023, March 24). *The story of India's scorched cities in four maps*. *Question of Cities*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

NRDC. 2022. "EXPANDING HEAT RESILIENCE ACROSS INDIA: HEAT ACTION PLAN HIGHLIGHTS 2022." Retrieved August 28, 2023.

CPR. 2023. "How Is India Adapting to Heatwaves?" Retrieved August 28, 2023.

Jaiswal, A. (2016, May 23). *A Tale of Three Cities: Heat Action Plans Across India*. NRDC. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

CEEW. (2024, March 15). *How can Heat Action Plans Make Thane a Heat-Resilient City?* CEEW. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Dutta, P. et al. (2022). "A Successful Heat Wave Prevention in Ahmedabad Calls for Segregated Health Record: Highlights from Existing Heat Action Plan." *Aerosol and Air Quality Research*. Retrieved August 28, 2023.

Hindu BusinessLine. 2022. "How Ahmedabad tackled its heat waves and saved 1,000 lives a year."

Times of India. (2023, April 4). "Summer buffer: India's first cool roof policy takes off in Telangana."

BEEP. (2018). *Case Study on "Green" Affordable Housing: Smart GHAR III, Rajkot*. INDO-SWISS BUILDING ENERGY EFFICIENCY PROJECT (BEEP).

WWF. (2021, June 7). *Rajkot – Efficient cooling is key*. WWF.

BEE. (2017). *Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC) | BUREAU OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY*, Government of India, Ministry of Power. Bureau of Energy Efficiency.

Chandigarh: City Beautiful getting hotter by the decade

Chandigarh recorded the hottest day in September 2023 in 36 years. The maximum temperature recorded was 3.9°C above normal for the month of September. According to the IMD, Chandigarh has witnessed a 1.78°C rise in the average minimum temperature since 1950. While the average maximum temperature has seen a rise of 0.63°C. The rise in the minimum temperature of the city is higher

The city witnessed hottest March in 2022 in last 12 years!

Figure 14 : Rise in average Maximum & Minimum Temperature during March & overall rise in past 70 years
Source: IMD; Chandigarh growing hotter by the decade | HT

than the rise in India's mean temperature during the period 1901-2018, which is 0.7°C.

The data reveals that there has been an increase in average minimum and maximum temperatures every month from 1950 to 1980 and from 1980 to 2010 in Chandigarh. The highest increase has been seen in the month of February. With a minimum temperature of 18.8°C, the city recorded the warmest February in 2021 since 2011.

The reduction in forest cover, unchecked urbanisation, increased use of private vehicles, and population explosion have collectively led Chandigarh to become an Urban Heat Island (UHI). Experts attribute this increase in average temperatures to the higher concentration of greenhouse gases present in the city. Urbanization has led to the concretization of the city, which

Figure 15 : Rise in temperatures in Chandigarh- Causes and Results
Source: Chandigarh becomes urban heat island | India Today

is responsible for trapping heat and raising the temperature. Additionally, vehicular emissions are also contributing to this temperature rise. Data by the Regional Licencing Authority shows a 50 fold increase in vehicle ownership in Chandigarh from 1974 to 2018. Rising temperatures are also closely linked to reduced rainfall. The city recorded 39% less rainfall in August 2021 and 41% less rainfall in August 2022 compared to normal levels.

References

Singh, R. (2023). Chandigarh records hottest September day in 36 years. *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Hindustan Times. 2019. "Chandigarh growing hotter by the decade."

MoES. (2021). *Assessment of Climate Change over the Indian Region*. Springer Nature. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

PIB. (2023, August 2). *Impact of Climate Change upon the Indian subcontinent*. PIB. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Tribune India. (2021). "Chandigarh records warmest Feb night in 12 years."

India Today. (2019). "Title:Chandigarh becomes urban heat island, minimum temperature rises by 1 degree in 3 decades."

Tribune India. (2021). "Driest August in 5 years, Chandigarh recorded 39% deficit rainfall."

Singh, R. (2022). Chandigarh | August recorded 41% rain shortfall. *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved April 18, 2024.

Repository

Important Reads

IMD Annual Summary
Reports

<https://www.imdpune.gov.in/lr/index.php>

Climatological Normals of
1981-2020

<https://www.imdpune.gov.in/library/public/Climatological%20Tables%201991-2020.pdf>

Hazard Atlas of India

<https://imdpune.gov.in/hazardatlas/heatnew.html>

Climate Data Service
Portal (CDSP)

<https://cdsp.imdpune.gov.in/index.php#projects>

Ahmedabad Heat Action
Plan

<https://www.nrdc.org/sites/default/files/ahmedabad-heat-action-plan-2016.pdf>

NDMA Guidelines for
Preparation of Heat
Action Plan

<https://nidm.gov.in/PDF/pubs/NDMA/27.pdf>

